

Final Report on WP4: Project-specific assistance, help desk, and advanced user support

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Norwegian AI cloud(NAIC)

Building the foundation for Norway's AI sovereignty with Compute and Competence

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Work package and deliverables final report

WP4: Project-specific assistance, help desk, and advanced user support

Glossary of Terms

Term	Description
Advanced User Support (AUS)	In-depth, technical and project-specific assistance provided to NAIC users handling complex AI/ML workloads, utilizing established Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services (Sigma2/NRIS) procedures.
Central Help Desk	The primary support interface for NAIC users. It is integrated directly with the NRIS first-line support system, which receives incoming inquiries and routes AI-related tickets to specialized NAIC staff.
Discourse	The forum software platform selected and configured to serve as NAIC's GDPR-compliant user-to-user support and community platform (https://naicforum.online).
Fox / Saga / Olivia	High-Performance Computing (HPC) clusters utilized by WP4 staff to run job scripts, deploy local Large Language Models, and process large datasets for project-specific use cases.
LLM-RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation)	An AI framework combining Large Language Models with document retrieval systems. WP4 utilized this architecture to develop custom chatbots, such as the history bot on Wittgenstein's literary works and the bot for the NAIC competence map.
NIRD (National Infrastructure for Research Data)	A national data storage and compute infrastructure operated by Sigma2, where NAIC-WP4 members applied for and utilized computing resources.
NRIS (Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services)	The organization providing the frontline support infrastructure. Emails sent to the NAIC support address land in the NRIS first-line system before being labeled Team NAIC (or [naic-support]) and distributed to WP4.

Term	Description
Ollama / Llama.cpp	Tools and frameworks utilized by WP4 staff to execute local, open-weight Large Language Models (such as Llama 3.1 and Qwen2.5-VL) on HPC clusters.
Slurm	A workload manager and job scheduling system used on the HPC clusters to queue and execute heavy AI workloads and scripts.
Streamlit / Gradio	Python frameworks investigated and utilized by the WP4 team to build simple, intuitive web-based user interfaces for data preprocessing and LLM inference.
NAIF	AKA KI-fabrikken , the national AI factory in Norway, which is supposed to become a national hub for artificial intelligence (AI), research, and innovation. Together with other national key players, they plan to ensure that AI becomes more accessible for research, the public sector, and industry.
NCC	The National Competence Center for HPC. Assists private industry, with a particular focus on small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), and public administration in developing expertise in the use of advanced technology, such as:

1. Executive Summary

This report summarizes the achievements of Work Package 4 (WP4) in establishing comprehensive user support and project-specific assistance for the Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC). NAIC WP4 gained valuable insights about user needs and patterns, informing future national research support offerings in Norway.

- **Central Help Desk & Competence Mapping:** WP4 successfully launched a central help desk integrated with the NRIS first-line support system. To ensure efficient ticket routing and resolution, the team created a competence map of NAIC staff.
- **Project-Specific Assistance:** The team provided in-depth technical and AI guidance, and HPC resources for five complex AI projects, yielding high user satisfaction. Key successes included employing local LLMs for secure document summarization, multimodal LLMs to enable transcription of 6.6 million handwritten census pages, secure AI pipelines for analyzing administrative court judgments, and a RAG-LLM chatbot for a philosophical literary knowledge base.
- **Advanced User Support (AUS):** WP4 successfully adapted existing Sigma2/NRIS procedures to help users secure GPU-enabled hardware on NREC and NIRD for demanding AI/ML workloads.

Recommendation The most evident conclusion from the work package is that the current NRIS Sigma2 support model works well for users who already know what they need, but leaves a significant gap for researchers who could benefit from AI and machine learning (ML) yet lack the competence, confidence, or entry point to move forward. This gap became especially visible through the **Project Specific Assistance (PSA)** activity. By proactively engaging research groups, PSA showed that many researchers do not need only technical support—they need help identifying where AI and ML are relevant to their research in the first place. While many are now familiar with LLM-based tools for writing and general assistance, far fewer understand or possess sufficient competence on how AI and ML can be applied to their own data, methods, and research problems. When researchers were proactively engaged and given access to AI/ML expertise, this frequently led to valuable advanced support projects that would otherwise not have been initiated. With user support now transferred to NRIS Sigma2, the national support offering consists of **HelpDesk, Enhanced User Support (EUS), and Advanced User Support (AUS)**. These are strong and necessary services, but the PSA experience shows that they are not sufficient on their own. Two actions are now needed.

The first is to increase AI/ML competence and capacity in NRIS Sigma2 Support. Current capacity is too limited to meet the emerging demand, and we therefore recommend adding at least **1 FTE dedicated to AI and ML support**. This resource should complement, rather than duplicate, the work of Norwegian AI Factory (NAIF) or National Competence Centre for HPC (NCC), as the two other initiatives have different objectives and distinct mandates, and target

separate primary user groups.

The second is to move from a purely reactive to a more proactive support model. NRIS should actively reach out to research groups, create more opportunities for dialogue, and improve visibility of available services. This effort should be coordinated across NRIS, including Sigma2's communication function, and anchored in the proposed AI/ML expert role. WP4 therefore calls for three concrete actions:

1. Add 1 FTE in AI/ML support capacity within NRIS Sigma2 Support model.
2. Establish a more proactive outreach model toward research groups and projects.
3. Continue and expand the communication and marketing of NRIS service offerings, including available AI and ML support, beyond NAIF and NCC.

Without these steps, an important part of the research community will remain underserved. With them, NRIS Sigma2 can take a stronger national role in enabling broader and more effective use of AI in Norwegian research.

2. Work package deliverables and tasks

2.1 Central help desk (D4.3)

Establishing a central help desk for supporting user

Figure 1: relationships WP4

2.1.1 Overview *Fig.1: Venn diagram depicting relationship among work package 4 (WP4), Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC) and Norwegian research infrastructure*

services (NRIS).

Deliverable goals The primary objective was to establish of a Central Help Desk for The Norwegian AI Cloud (NAIC) to provide comprehensive support and guidance to users of the AI infrastructure. The central help desk serves as the primary contact for both basic and advanced user support, including project-specific needs; ensuring users have a single point of contact. * Provide a centralized platform for engaging in discussion with users to comprehend their issues and expectations. * Assisting users in navigating the complexities of the AI ecosystem, tools, or platforms provided by NAIC. * Offering assistance and solving technical or methodological challenges that users encounter.

Target audience Users of NAIC resources: * **Students:** undergraduate and mostly graduate students for AI tasks in their thesis/projects. * **Researchers:** early-career and senior researchers using NAIC resources for AI tasks. * **Industry partners:** companies collaborating with NAIC on applied AI projects.

2.1.2 Output/Result WP4 successfully established operational protocols for the central help desk, which serves as a main component of user support. We utilized the resources of a successful collaborative e-infrastructure in Norway called Norwegian research infrastructure services (NRIS) as NRIS serving researchers from various Norwegian universities with their national High-Performance Computing (HPC) and storage facilities for several years.

Helpdesk pipeline The helpdesk consists of different core and assistive components:

I) Central help desk The procedure of the central help desk is described here.

a) NAIC-related tickets are initially handled and labeled by the NRIS first-line support team. Users typically receive a response within 2–3 hours from the first-line. The first line escalates unsolved NAIC-related tickets to the second line, the NAIC support desk. These tickets receive the header [naic-support] or label TEAM|NAIC.

The domain of NAIC-related support includes: **(i)** data processing libraries such as Pandas and NumPy; **(ii)** generative AI platforms like Ollama and Hugging Face, as well as APIs available via Azure, Google, and OpenAI; **(iii)** core machine and deep learning frameworks including TensorFlow, PyTorch, Keras, Scikit-learn, and **Fast.ai**; **(iv)** automated machine learning (AutoML) solutions such as AutoKeras, Google Cloud AutoML, and PyCaret; **(v)** visualization and interpretability tools like Matplotlib, Seaborn, and TensorBoard.

While not exhaustive, this list covers a wide range of tools that support different stages of the AI/ML lifecycle. The NAIC-related ticket and its domains are briefly explained at the provided NRIS and NAIC documentation links.

b) The NAIC-WP4 support team addresses the ticket within 5 working days. **c)** If the case requires more time and aligns with NAIC’s objectives, it is transferred

to project-specific assistance. Project-specific assistance may take more than 1–3 months, depending on the expectations and deliverables of the case.

Fig.2: Working flow between users and central help desk

During this period, we use a “Jungle guide concept” where users present problems related to AI use cases, and we provide tailored advice and support.

II) Assistive tool developed and employed The following tools have been developed or employed to enhance both user experience and support services.

- (a) User-help-user platform** A common forum was established where users can seek and provide assistance, guidance, or solutions with moderation to each other through <https://naicforum.online/> using Discourse community platform. This kind of forum facilitates users in harnessing collective experiences and promoting collaboration.
- A pilot forum was hosted and tested: naicforum.online
 - Categories defined (Training, AI, HPC, Technical Support, Community).
 - Branding and basic theming applied with NAIC identity.
 - Tested integration options: SSO, and potential plugin use.
 - Tutorial session with Flinkcube (Discourse provider) delivered to WP4 team.

(b) Chatbots We have developed a prototype of a Large Language Model (LLM)-Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) based chatbot on NRIS documentation (documentation.sigma2.no) to assist both the first line and second line staff. The NRIS documentation consisting of 275+ markdown files are used as the knowledge base of the chatbot. Both first line and second line staff can leverage the advantage of the chatbot to respond to user’s queries. The chatbot is deployed at chat.nris.no. The support staff can use it after successfully authenticating with one’s NRIS gmail id.

2.1.3 Impact & dissemination

- Shared at the official page of NAIC (<https://www.naic.no/naic-support-desk/>) and documented at NRIS/NAIC internal documentation page.
- Presented our chatbot at several local and national events (e.g., NRIS AHM 2024).

2.1.4 Risks & challenges

- Finding collaborators from other institutes as they often hesitate to attend the central help desk.

- Long-term attendance and maintenance.
- GDPR issue to include non-NRIS members to the central helpdesk.

2.1.5 Sustainability & future work

- Next steps: Interfacing with non-NRIS members with best practices (following GDPR).
- Interfacing with Lumi user support system (LUST, following GDPR).

2.2 Competence map (D4.2)

2.2.1 Overview Description and goal The staff competence map provides a structured overview of the skills and expertise of team members. It documents individual competencies across relevant areas to support effective task allocation. The primary objective was to develop a competence map of staff, enabling the support system to be staffed by individuals with the necessary expertise.

2.2.2 Output/Result

- A competence map has been created showing the skills available for the support line. The competence map includes fields such as role/tasks, background, main competence, areas of experience, and activities enjoyed.
- We have developed a prototype of an LLM-RAG Bot on NRIS's competence map. The bot will be useful for the firstline staff while assigning tickets to a person whose skill aligns with his competence.
- The developed prototype of the LLM-RAG Bot has been tested by our colleagues and accurately recommends individuals based on their skills.

2.2.3 Impact & dissemination The competence map is shared at NRIS's infohub so that NRIS first line staff can transfer/forward tickets to the second line staff (NAIC Staff), where tickets' required skills match with the staff's competence.

2.2.4 Risks & challenges Staff often do not update their skills when they acquire new ones. Additionally, they may hesitate to rate their own skill levels on a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 is low and 10 is high, as sharing whether they are highly or less skilled can be uncomfortable. An outdated or incomplete competence map may hinder effective ticket assignments.

2.2.5 Sustainability & future work

- Maintain a regularly updated competence map.
- Document each competence area alongside the individual's skill level.
- Identify and develop skills currently lacking in individuals.

2.2.6 Notes/comments It is ideal to have a competence map that lists each competence area along with the individual’s skill level (rated 1–10, where 1 is low and 10 is high). Competence areas can include C/C++, CI/CD, computer vision, deep learning, DevOps, Docker, Git/Github, HPC, Kubernetes, machine learning, PyTorch, Ray, Scikit-learn, Slurm, Tensorflow, visualization, and related skillset. This format of competence map helps assign tickets to the most suitable person based on the complexity of the issue. Additionally, it supports organizing and planning training sessions to enhance the skills of staff needed for specific projects.

2.3 Project specific assistance (D4.1)

2.3.1 Overview Project description The project specific assistance offers technical, methodological, and resource-oriented support tailored to the needs of individual AI projects.

Goal/objectives * Identify user challenges through systematic engagement. * Facilitate access to NAIC resources. * Provide technical and methodological guidance for project tasks. * Recommend and assist with customized solutions related to data handling, computation, and other resource needs. * Sharing support outcomes—such as scripts, code implementations, and shareable subsets of data—to promote transparency and reproducibility.

Target audience * Researchers and educators: undergraduate and mostly graduate students, early-career, senior researchers, and educators. * State organizations: state organizations collaborating with NAIC on applied AI/HPC projects.

2.3.2 Status What has been achieved Project-specific assistance team has supported approximately five projects, resulting in good user satisfaction given the available resources. The team has played a vital role in empowering users to achieve impactful results, potentially contributing to the advancement of AI applications in Norway. Staff involved have gained valuable competence and experience throughout the process, which may benefit their institutions.

List of completed projects in NAIC

a) Survey summarization using a large language model (LLM) and manual assessment The Kunnskapsdepartementet (KUD) provided proprietary survey documents for summarization using an LLM in a local environment. The objective was to generate summaries with open-weight language models, ensuring that the documents are not exposed to external platforms and model APIs. In order to ensure the reliability and accuracy of summaries produced by the language model, it is necessary to carry out manual assessments of the generated outputs. This review process is essential for evaluating both the syntactic quality (grammar, and sentence structure) and the contextual correctness (accuracy, and relevance). While automated evaluation methods can provide partial insights, they are not sufficient to guarantee high-quality results. Human judgment

remains critical to verifying that the documents meet established standards of clarity, precision, and appropriateness. To achieve these objectives, we employed the open-weight model Llama 3.1(70B), utilizing the University of Oslo (UiO)'s Educloud GPU resources. To evaluate the outputs of the language model, we performed a manual assessment process. Each generated summary was reviewed alongside its corresponding source document to ensure both semantic accuracy and contextual fidelity. The evaluation involved assigning two distinct scores on a five-point scale: one for syntactic quality (including grammar, sentence structure, and overall readability), and one for contextual quality (covering accuracy, relevance, and alignment with the source content). The provided setup, along with source code, enables the user to process those documents and generate summaries.

Challenges and future work: * Prompt-based approaches using available open-weight models may not produce summaries in the expected structure. * Fine-tuning LLMs can be explored to specialize the model for generating summaries in Norwegian and in the desired format. * There is a lack of labeled data required for fine-tuning. * Manual assessment of the syntactic and contextual quality of generated summaries is time-intensive.

b) Handwriting Recognition (HWR) of large volumes semi-structured documents The project Handwriting Recognition (HWR) of large volumes semi-structured documents aims to develop an LLM driven pipeline for transcribing, extracting, and converting handwritten population and housing censuses into standardized data and metadata formats. Current manual transcription (crowdsourcing/low-cost workforce) is costly, resource-intensive, produces errors, includes bias from transcribers, and yields selective transcription and is therefore incomplete. The selective transcription is aimed at genealogical research, while complete transcription is aimed at historical, economic, and social research. The goal is to transcribe the complete 1920 Norwegian census (6.6 million pages of scanned documents). By using LLM, the project will substantially reduce the cost of transcription, revision, and correction. To achieve these objectives, WP4 provided secure HPC environments (Saga cluster), and local multimodal LLM deployments (Qwen3-VL). Multimodal LLMs (like Qwen3-VL) were deployed on the cluster to transcribe images to texts using Slurm scripts. A ResNet-18 model was trained to classify the front and back of scanned documents. The provided source code enables the user to process over 6.6 million pages of census forms, provided he meets the computing requirements for this resource-intensive task.

Challenges and future work: * The current version doesn't work well with underlined/marked fields. * The current version doesn't work well with badly handwritten fields. * Explore possibilities of specialized models for detecting underlined/marked fields. * Explore fine-tuning LLMs in-order to make the model more specialized for Norwegian handwritings. * Currently there are 33 people older than 105 years in Norway and they probably are recorded in the source as it was recorded 1. December 1920. Since data contains medical information, it is important that the data is processed in Norway. The data is

no longer protected by the Statistikk-loven, which safeguards this type of data for publication in 100 years (e.g. data newer than 1925).

c) Court-judgement-LLM-transcription As part of the Research Council-funded EXPUN project (coordinated by Faculty of Law, University of Bergen), the research team has gained access to several hundred administrative decisions. The researchers want to develop an LLM-based solution to systematically organise and interpret this material, supporting both exploratory analysis and standardised extraction of relevant information. Administrative decisions are often based on legal criteria that are vague and ambiguous. The discretion employed can vary significantly from one officer to another, potentially leading to inconsistencies and arbitrariness in the final judgements. To address this issue, implementing a Generative AI (GenAI)-assisted pipeline could help the research team to systematically analyse a larger number of administrative decisions to see how the discretion is employed.

The codebase is created according to the following principles: * Avoid incorrect or fabricated responses as much as possible. * Reduce subjectivity and promote greater consistency and fairness. * The code base should be implemented on a safe-server (air-gapped) because of the sensitivity of the data.

We setup computing resource on UiB-SAFE (Sikker Adgang til Forskningsdata og E-infrastruktur, uib.no/safe) with necessary tools (Ollama + an open weight LLM). We provided source code that enables users to test and analyze court judgements using prompts designed for information extraction.

Challenges and future work: * The pipeline is designed to work on an air-gapped system (UiB-SAFE). This system either lacks a GPU or has limited GPU memory; therefore, a small LLM was selected to ensure it would run successfully. The model is easy to change if the system limitations change, which could provide better text understanding/reasoning. * LLMs may hallucinate and are not deterministic; results may change. * Organize development from current status to deployment. * The dataset cannot be shared due to its sensitive content.

d) History bot on literary works of Wittgenstein This project aims to develop a prototype of a chatbot on Wittgenstein Nachlass, the Wittgenstein Archives at the University of Bergen (WAB, <https://wab.uib.no/>).

The goal of the chatbot is to adhere to the following principles: * The chatbot shall avoid incorrect or fabricated responses as much as possible. * The chatbot shall encourage and assist users in double-checking the chatbot's answers. * The chatbot shall facilitate easy access to WAB's other online resources and tools.

A prototype was developed using OpenAI APIs (GPT-5.1-chat, etc.) and deployed as an Azure Web App in a Docker container.

We have achieved following functionalities: * The current version of the Bot covers the entire Wittgenstein Nachlass within a single, unified interface. * It (the current version) provides more comprehensive answers across Wittgenstein's corpus compared to earlier pilots. * It improves reliability compared to earlier

pilots. * It displays verifiable source references at the end of each response, enabling users to trace claims to the primary materials. * It handles metadata and date frames with higher accuracy than earlier pilots. * It can appropriately return negative results (“no relevant remarks found”) when the knowledge base provides no evidence. * It retrieves conceptually relevant passages beyond exact word matches. * It integrates with WAB’s online infrastructure, extending and enhancing existing research tools (e.g. SFB).

The provided source code enables users to modify the chatbot’s behavior according to their future needs.

Challenges and future work: * The current version of the Bot does not implement conversational style. * It scores low on completeness of answers. * It has biases towards certain parts of the knowledge base. * It sometimes hallucinates in terms of adding irrelevant (but existing) sources. It is sometimes ignorant, i.e. it answers “I don’t know” where it should know. * It has mistakes in the dates. It has limitations when answering prompts with date frames.

e) Infrastructure support for reinforcement learning This project explores the application of deep reinforcement learning for controlling compressor frequency in heat pumps, aiming to increase building energy efficiency. The research involves training a masked version of the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm, which requires access to GPU resources for efficient experimentation and analysis. The objective is to develop and evaluate deep reinforcement learning models for optimal compressor control in heat pumps, utilizing GPU infrastructure facilitated by NAIC to ensure timely completion of experiments and result analysis ahead of the 46th IAEE International Conference in Paris, June 2025. To achieve this, a slurm managed virtual cluster was provided inside the NAIC after several rounds of discussions. The user was able to successfully complete his task using NAIC infrastructure and project specific support.

2.3.3 Risks & Challenges

- Datasets often can’t be shared because they contain sensitive information.
- Risks and challenges for each project are documented in their respective sections in 2.3.3(a-e).

2.3.4 Feasibility of transferring project-specific assistance practices to NRIS The support staff should have both theoretical and practical knowledge of AI, including machine learning and generative AI, as well as familiarity with state-of-the-art tools and libraries relevant to AI projects. User needs vary; some require comprehensive support from the outset, while others require assistance only when encountering challenges at specific stages. To provide effective support, staff should demonstrate the necessary expertise and problem-solving skills. However, the level of competence and extensive user engagement required may exceed the current personnel capacity of NRIS.

2.4 Advanced user support (AUS, D4.4)

The Advanced User Support strategy builds upon existing Sigma2/NRIS procedures, tailored specifically for AI/ML workloads. * **Procedures:** AUS requests utilize established Sigma2 frameworks but incorporate provisions specific to AI and ML, such as VM provisioning via the NAIC Orchestrator. * **Resource Allocation:** WP4 successfully assisted users in securing necessary HPC resources, such as GPU-enabled hardware on NREC and NIRD, to support deep learning research.

3. Deviations

Nothing to report.